

CHARACTERIZATION OF THE MECHANICAL PROPERTY BEHAVIOR OF SELECTED GRAPHITE FIBER REINFORCED ALUMINUM ALLOYS

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Abstract

An on-going program to characterize the room and elevated temperature mechanical property behavior of several continuous and discontinuous fiber-reinforced aluminum-alloy composite systems is described. Specific data are presented on the tensile, compressive and shear properties at room temperature and at temperatures in the range of 300 to 900⁰ F. Emphasis is placed upon the Thornel 50 (T-50) graphite-fiber reinforced 201 aluminum alloy system. Preliminary data on other graphite fibers, and discontinuous silicon carbide whisker composites are also presented. The test techniques employed and the calibration experiments conducted are described. A summary of both room and elevated temperature data on these composites is presented.

Introduction

Several continuous and discontinuous fiber reinforced metal matrix composite systems are currently under development by the Naval Sea Systems Command (NSSC) to meet the future needs of the Navy for advanced weapons and Naval platforms. One of these programs is sponsored by the Materials and Mechanics Division of NSSC and is technically directed by the Naval Surface Weapons Center NSWC). The program was initiated in 1974 and is directed toward the development of new materials and materials-fabrication and processing techniques to provide improved systems performance capability.

One of the major technologies being addressed is the development of aluminum alloy metal matrix composites for elevated temperature structural applications. This paper summarizes some of the elevated temperature characterization studies conducted thus far under NSSC and NSWC sponsorship. Since this work is continuing it is presented as a report on the progress attained to date. Emphasis is placed on the characterization of a production baseline graphite fiber reinforced aluminum system (Gr/Al) comprised of Thornel 50 (T-50) fibers in a 201 aluminum alloy matrix simply designated as T50/201. Data on newer graphite fiber systems having significantly improved properties are also presented although this information must be considered preliminary because of the limited number of tests conducted thus far. Similar data are also presented on low cost discontinuous silicon carbide whisker composite systems which must be viewed in the same context.

History of the Development of Graphite/Aluminum Composites

One of the very early investigations of (Gr/Al) composites was conducted in 1961 by Koppenaal and Parikh(1). They employed powder metallurgical techniques to prepare a 20 to 40 vol % chopped-fiber composite preform which was then hot-extruded. Although the properties of the extruded composite were stronger than the extruded (nonreinforced) aluminum-4% copper matrix alloy used, the strength of the graphite fibers available at that time was so low as to seriously limit the final composite properties obtained. For example, ultimate tensile strength attained was less than 35,000 psi.

In the 1966-1971 time period, Sara, et.al., (2-4) attempted to pressure-impregnate aluminum into graphite-fiber yarn bundles with limited success. They concluded that pressure alone was insufficient to promote complete infiltration and that the wetting of graphite by aluminum was necessary in order to achieve good infiltration. Sara then tried a variety of materials (TiC, Ta, NbC, Ni) to act as interfacial reaction barriers and as wetting agents. Fiber degradation, incomplete coatings, and other problems were identified in this work and the work of later investigators (5) who began employing chemical vapor deposition technology for the interface layer. Several investigators (6-9) have utilized electroplating as a technique for applying interfacial layers. From the majority of work conducted through the 1960's and even into the early 1970's, it was concluded by many that no single fabrication method or combinations of methods could consistently attain rule-of-mixtures strengthening for Gr/Al composites. Various investigators could often successfully demonstrate one step of the total processing technology, but no one group, up to this time, had succeeded in carrying out all the necessary steps so as to consistently attain a high translation of the properties of the two constituents.

In 1968, The Aerospace Corporation began a research program aimed at creation of graphite fiber reinforced metal matrix composites. Selection of graphite as the reinforcement was based upon cost and availability as well as its demonstrated thermal and mechanical properties. The process chosen for development was liquid metal infiltration of fiber bundles. Initially, two processes were studied. Both processes emphasized formation of a protective coating on the graphite fibers which would permit wetting of the fiber with the molten matrix metal. The first process to be developed involved the use of sodium and tin to form an intermetallic coating on the graphite with subsequent liquid metal infiltration. This process showed potential for making graphite-aluminum and graphite-lead composites with rule of mixtures longitudinal mechanical properties. However, problems in controlling the amounts of residual sodium in the graphite fiber and costly scaleup problems made this process appear less attractive than the subsequently developed process utilizing a titanium-boron protective coating.

In 1970, Kendall and Pepper (10), of the Aerospace Corporation, reported on the successful infiltration and consolidation of Gr/Al composites made using a chemically vapor deposited titanium-boron interfacial coating on the surface of graphite yarns followed by controlled immersion in a molten aluminum bath. The actual process was termed "Liquid Metal Impregnation". Later that year, Kendall, Pepper and co-workers (11-13) demonstrated the ability to consistently attain rule-of-mixtures strengths over a wide range of fiber loadings using aluminum-silicon alloys. Subsequent work extended the technology to other aluminum-base matrix alloys.

Navy programs for the development of Gr/Al composites began in 1972 with a program (14) to evaluate all applicable methods for making Gr/Al composites and to recommend one process for further development optimization. The liquid-metal-infiltration process emerged as the only real viable candidate and shortly thereafter the Navy accelerated its support of a basic technology program. (It is interesting to note in passing that Nixdorf and co-workers (15) at Battelle-Frankfort Laboratories had been working during the same time period (1971-1973) and had independently arrived at the same conclusion regarding the viability of the

liquid metal infiltration approach for the fabrication of Gr/Al precursor wire.) Late in 1973 an applications program was initiated. Subsequent trade off studies were conducted under this program by Pfeifer and Yates (16) which indicated the desirability of accelerating the development of Gr/Al technology.

Applications trade off studies were initiated in mid 1974. The purpose of these studies was to perform a systems trade-off to assess the potential usefulness of advanced composite materials for systems applications in the 1980's. The immediate short-term objective was to initiate a broad examination of new materials in view of projected requirements and to develop a systematic rationale for selecting a limited number of the most promising materials for further study and development.

Results of these studies (14)-(16) revealed that the materials which showed the greatest potential for future applications were (1) high-strength (HS) and high-modulus (HM) graphites in aluminum, (2) HS and HM graphites in epoxy, phenolic and polyimide and (3) HS and HM graphites in thermoplastics. While a wide variance in degree of risk existed between materials they were all considered worthy of further development effort and study for future application.

The Phase I trade-off studies described above clearly identified the graphite/aluminum system as one of the most promising metal-matrix composite candidates for further development.

Accordingly, the second phase of the program, i.e., the development of the necessary materials technology to support the design, analysis, testing and evaluation of full-size hardware, was initiated. Critical programs now being performed include conceptual design studies and materials fabrication and characterization studies. Details of these Gr/Al characterization studies have been reported by Pfeifer and Young (17). Preliminary design studies have been completed and reported by Rezin (18).

Discontinuous Reinforcements

New interest in discontinuous whisker reinforced aluminum alloys developed similarly during the course of the Navy studies. This interest was renewed because of the availability of low cost pitch matte from Union Carbide and Exxon's potentially low cost silicon carbide whiskers manufactured from rice hulls.

Early studies of composites fabricated from these newly available low cost pitch fiber reinforcements were conducted by Pfeifer (19) in the 1973-1974 period. During these studies, discontinuous fiber reinforced composite extrusion billets were examined from several commercial sources. Composite billets were characterized and extrusion parameters were developed.

It was shown that the limiting materials technology was the preparation of high density, high quality starting billets. Billets containing residual porosity from 5 to 15% were easily extruded. However, this porosity was not metallurgically healed during hot extrusion, and the strengths of the resulting extrusions were less than the parent aluminum alloys.

However, billets prepared using a modified casting process proved to be an exception. Initial samples studied (19) consisted of both graphite and silicon carbide whiskers in 2024 and 1100 aluminum. Ultimate tensile strengths equal to those of the aluminum alloy matrix were easily attained with tensile moduli increased by 30 to 50% over the matrix alloy.

Based upon these very limited results, NSWC initiated a program at NETCO to continue the development of these materials for Navy applications. Initial results of these ongoing studies have been reported by Pfeifer (20) and the latest data are described herein.

Description of Materials and Experimental Procedures

Materials

One of the major advantages of fiber reinforced metals, retention of strength and stiffness at elevated temperatures, is being investigated for two types of composite systems. The first type is a composite consisting of a dispersion of discontinuous silicon carbide (SiC) whiskers in various aluminum alloys; the second system consists of a sandwich construction of continuous graphite fiber reinforcements in an aluminum alloy matrix. The SiC/AL is a randomly orientated discontinuous whisker composite while the Gr/Al is the classical highly orientated continuous fiber composite. Techniques used for the preparation of both types of composites are summarized below.

Graphite-Aluminum Composites (Gr/Al)

An extensive review of Gr/Al materials infiltration and consolidation technology is presented by Pfeifer in reference (21). For the current study, T-50/201 Gr/Al precursor wire, containing a nominal 32% Thornel fibers and having a diameter of approximately 0.050", was consolidated into a three layer laminate type construction referred to as "Baseline" Gr/Al. This material configuration, shown schematically in Figure 1, results in a unidirectionally reinforced composite having a nominal thickness of 0.105" when eight ended T-50/201 precursor wire is used. The laminate construction consists of .006" of 2024 Al foil on top and bottom surfaces with three layers of the precursor Gr/Al composite wire "sandwiched" in between those foils. The initial diameter and geometry of the precursor wire determines to a large extent the final thickness of the consolidated laminate. A similar laminate fabricated using Celanese Gy70 fibers in 201 Al alloy produces a three layer panel thickness of approximately 0.070" for Gy70/201 precursor wire having an initial diameter of 0.025". The diameter of the Gr/Al precursor wire is a function of the individual fiber geometry, the number of fibers per strand, the number of strands per tow, and the degree of twist, if any. These fiber characteristics influence the wire packing density during layup which in turn greatly influences the consolidation efficiency of various laminates. Irregularly shaped precursor wire which is incompletely consolidated can result in entrapped porosity of the type shown in Figure 2. (Fully consolidated material is shown in Figure 3.)

Figure 1. T50/201 ("BASELINE") GRAPHITE ALUMINUM COMPOSITE

• There are several variations possible in sandwich construction and it is important to know the exact material configuration in order to understand the mechanical properties of the resultant composite panel. This is particularly true for all properties which are expected to be matrix dependent properties, i.e.,

transverse tensile strength. Variations in the number of precursor wire layers have been prepared resulting in monolayer, bilayer, and baseline (three layer) and other designations. Aluminum alloy foils have also been used around individual precursor wire bundles and this product is referred to as "encapsulated".

Figure 2. Microstructure from T50/201 Gr/Al metallographic specimen #B813-D selected from "bad" (anomalous) region of C-Scan record showing delaminated surface foils (bottom photo) and non-bonded precursor wire-wire interfaces (top photo) (Reference 17).

Figure 3. Microstructure from T50/201 Gr/Al metallographic specimen #B813-A selected from good region of C-Scan record. This microstructure is representative of the majority of an 8" x 13" x .100" thick Gr/Al composite panel (Reference 17).

From the above it should be self evident that a wide variety of material forms exist which creates a "family" of Gr/Al composite materials having a broad range of properties. This offers the additional advantage to the designer of being able to offer great flexibility in tailoring the properties of a particular Gr/Al combination for a given application.

The majority of the materials described in this paper consist of the baseline three layer configuration. However, data is given for a few other configurations and these are identified accordingly. In the final analysis it is the fiber volume loading and the uniformity of the aluminum alloy matrix which ultimately determine the optimum achievable composite properties for a given fiber/matrix system.

Discontinuous SiC/Al Composites

A modified pressure casting process developed by Divecha (22) was utilized to randomly disperse 0.1μ diameter SiC whiskers in 2024 and 7075 aluminum alloy matrices. These billets were then hydrostatically hot extruded and rolled at 500°C to produce plate and sheet specimens. Details of the fabrication processes are given in reference (20).

Non Destructive Examination of Test Panels

All composite test panels were subjected to radiographic and ultrasonic (C Scan) inspection techniques before any test specimens were machined. In this way gross defects (such as porosity) which sometimes occur in poorly consolidated Gr/Al panels, could be avoided. Metallographic examinations were utilized to confirm microstructural defects occurring in anomalous regions of suspect panels. After the NDT inspections were completed, machining diagrams were laid out on the panel and specimens were machined to desired configuration using either diamond or bonded silicon carbide cut off wheels.

Test Techniques and Experimental Procedures

Graphite-Aluminum (Gr/Al) composites are a complex material, from a testing standpoint, in that they are highly anisotropic and therefore complicated to test. Several important factors must be considered in any successful testing and evaluation program. Clear test objectives, knowledge of the mechanics of composites and high quality test specimens are three important areas which contribute significantly to the value of any materials characterization program. The more common reasons for testing are materials research, processing development, engineering design and product quality control. In this program one of our interests is to understand how effectively initial fiber properties have been translated into composite forms during subsequent processing steps i.e., after the infiltration process to make precursor wire and the secondary consolidation (hot pressing) process to make test panels. Individual fiber tests are conducted according to ASTM D3379 "Standard Method of Test for Tensile Strength and Modulus of Elasticity for High Modulus Single Filament Materials" (23). Precursor Gr/Al wire tests are conducted according to the methods described in reference (24). Tests to determine fiber volume fraction tests are conducted in accordance with ASTM D3553 "Standard Test Method for Fiber Content by Digestion of Reinforced Metal Matrix Composites" (25).

Selected tests have been specifically designed to verify micro-mechanics analyses in order to better understand the behavior of the Gr/Al, particularly the fiber/matrix interfacial behavior. These tests are used to guide the overall materials selection process (i.e., choice of fiber and matrix) in order to provide direction to materials development activities. Off-axis tensile tests on unidirectional materials have been used to investigate shear properties and shear coupling effects.

The last type of testing activity involves the determination of properties to support an engineering design and in this case, we prefer to follow proven, well established "standard" tests to determine fundamental materials properties. For design studies we prefer tests that place the specimen under a simple, uniform state of stress. Furthermore, we make a clear distinction between the testing of a material system, a structural element, and a mechanical system.

In any emerging material system, test methods are always selected as a balance between specimen and/or equipment availability, and the cost to perform the test. The techniques employed in this program test were a balance of these considerations with the exception that wherever possible the principal consideration was to use "standard" test specimen configurations, sizes, and gripping and loading fixtures. Unfortunately, there are no universally accepted standard test methods for metal matrix composites, with the exception of the new ASTM D3552 (tensile properties (26)). However, there are ASTM standard methods in use by the various laboratories engaged in measuring the properties of resin matrix composites. These standards have been developed for the unique characteristics of composites. They specifically take into consideration the three significant differences between fiber reinforced composites and metals; i.e., the anisotropy, the absence of ductility and the very low shear properties relative to tensile and compressive properties.

A listing of specimen sizes and gripping techniques is given in Table 1. Details of each test technique are summarized below. Additional specific details are provided in reference (17).

Table 1. Specimen Sizes and Gripping Techniques

Test	Fiber Orientation	Width, in.	Length, in. Total Gage		Grip Type
Room Temperature Tensile	Longitudinal	.375	6	3.0	1½-2" long x .090" thick 1100 Al tabs adhesive bonded to specimen ends wedge action grips
	Transverse	.375	6	3.0	
Elevated Temperature Tensile	Longitudinal	.375	9	5	2" heated zone
	Transverse	.375	9	5	2" heated zone
Room Temperature Compression	Longitudinal and Transverse	0.400	0.6	0.400	0.1" long screw clamp in cylindrical ends .750" long hydraulic clamp sandwich beam, 4 point flex
		0.500	3	1.5	
	.250 .500	11	4		
Elevated Temperature Compression	Longitudinal and Transverse	.500	11	4	sandwich beam, 4 point flex
		.500	9	6	2" long x .090" thick 1100 tabs adhesive bond
Room Temperature Shear 15°					
Off Axis Tensile 45° 75°		.750		7	2" long x .090" 1100 Al tabs adhesives bonded to specimen ends
		1.00		8	
Pin Bearing Strength 0°, 45°, 90°		1½"		1½	¼" dia pin 2D from edge Adhesive bonded doublers
		1½"		1½	

Room Temperature Tensile Test

All tensile tests were conducted on straight sided coupon specimens similar to the configuration shown in ASTM standard method of test D-3039. The tabs of aluminum 1100-0 were square ended rather than bevelled as specified in D-3039 since no difference in the fracture location was found when bevelled end tabs were tried. A standard tab of $\frac{1}{2}$ " width was applied to the nominal $.375" \pm .010"$ wide specimens after measuring the width and thickness at three places along the length. The strain gages were adhesively mounted at the midlength and midwidth of the specimen gage length. The surface preparation for mounting of strain gages was a very light sanding and chemical cleaning to avoid thinning the foil surfaces of the composites. The tabbed and strain gaged specimens were gripped in standard wedge type grips containing serrated faces. The grips and universal test machine is a 20,000 Lb. capacity Instron (Model 1115).

Measurements of the alignment of the wedge action grips were made with a dial indicator and found to be within $\pm .002"$. The alignment of the specimen width to have the centerline coincide with the axis of the load cell was done by visual reference to grip edge. Cross head speeds of .020 and .050 inches per minute were utilized. As expected, no influence on the ultimate tensile strength has been found for tests at either crosshead speed.

The load and strain data are plotted as a stress-strain diagram. The tensile modulus of the specimen is computed for the initial straight line portion of the curve. The strain at fracture is also extrapolated from the stress-strain diagram.

Elevated Temperature Tensile Tests

The approach to characterize the elevated temperature mechanical properties of these materials considered four essential factors: (1) the necessity to control and accurately monitor specimen temperature (2) the necessity to minimize the amount of material consumed during testing (3) the anisotropy of the Gr/Al material and (4) the desirability of avoiding failure in the grips.

The sample materials in this work were in the form of thin plates varying from 0.050" to 0.110" thick. This dictated the use of coupon specimens which were gripped through wedge action jaws bearing on tabs bonded to the ends of the test specimen. The tab adhesives, which worked well for room temperature tests, could not be used at temperatures over 400°C. For this reason we chose to keep the central portion of a relatively long tensile specimen uniformly heated and allowed the grips to remain cool enough to maintain the required adhesive shear strength. Typical specimen configurations were $\frac{3}{8}$ " width by 6 to 8 inch lengths. Normally, two inch long aluminum tabs were used leaving 2" to 4" of gage section between tabs for room temperature tests. High temperature tests were conducted using 8" to 10" long specimens. A typical specimen, fully instrumented is shown in Figure 4. A few tests were made at room temperature using long specimens to verify the absence of a gage length effect. The specimens were heated in a clam shell furnace powered by opposing 1200 watt quartz lamps. The lamps actually heated a split stainless steel box which was 2" long and 2" wide. Insulation above and below the furnace was used to minimize the axial temperature gradient and keep the grips cool. The heating arrangement is shown in Figure 5. Considerable care was exercised in determining the axial temperature gradient along the specimen using thermocouples placed in small holes drilled in the edge of sample specimens. Thermocouples wired and centered on the specimen faces did not yield consistent temperatures due to the inability to maintain good thermal contact as the specimen was heated. Significantly improved results were achieved when specimen temperatures were measured by two face thermocouples peened into $\frac{1}{2}$ " square blocks of .090" aluminum which were then clamped on opposite sides of the specimen. The calibration experiments employed these face thermocouples with the internal temperatures read from thermocouples placed in holes drilled in the edge of the specimen. For test specimens the thermocouple blocks were located above the specimen center in order to provide space for strain gages. Calibration curves relating surface and internal specimen temperatures were developed for use over the range 300 to 900°F.

Figure 4. ELEVATED TEMPERATURE TEST SPECIMEN INSTRUMENTATION.

Tests were conducted in a 20,000 lb capacity Instron using manual control of the crosshead speed to step wise increase the load between strain readings. Specimens were soaked at temperature for five minutes to assure thermal equilibrium, and were exposed for another ten minutes during the actual test.

Compression Tests

Three test methods have been used to obtain the compressive properties. These tests include a concentric cylinder fixture, a modified IITRI fixture, and a honeycomb core sandwich beam loaded in four point bending. Each technique requires different specimen sizes. The approach to selection of a specimen geometry in order to eliminate buckling effects must account for the fact that the axial shear stiffness of unidirectional composites is much lower than the axial tensional stiffness. The reduced critical stress must be used to select the specimen thickness to avoid buckling. The relationship, is as follows: (27)

$$\sigma_{cr}^r = \frac{\sigma_{cr}}{1 + n \frac{\sigma_{cr}}{G}}$$

where:

- σ_{cr}^r = The reduced critical stress,
- σ_{cr} = Critical stress computed for isotropic materials
- n = shape factor ~ 1.2 for rectangular sections, and
- G = Axial shear modulus

Figure 5. Schematic of Specially Constructed Quartz Lamp Furnace Employed for Elevated Temperature Tests Conducted at Temperature up to 1000°F

The first test method utilizes a prismatic specimen of unidirectional T50/201 having a length of 0.6", a width of 0.4" and a thickness of ~ 0.1 . The fiber direction parallels the 0.6" dimension. Approximately 0.10" of each end of the specimen is clamped vise-like using a setscrew against a steep pad in the end of a right circular cylinder of steel. The arrangement is shown in Figure 6. The pair of cylinders (~ 1.720 " diameter x 1.0" long) are aligned on their axes by insertion into a tightly fitting cylindrical sleeve 2 1/4" long. The specimen end, a surface 0.4" x 0.1", is parallel to the cylinder end surfaces. This assembly is made up with one end of the specimen clamped after the two cylinders are contained in the sleeve to ensure axial alignment. The specimen gage length of ~ 0.40 " is unsupported and strain gages of 1/16" length are mounted in the midwidth and midlength of the specimen on each face to monitor bending. The two cylinders and support sleeve are placed between the compression anvils of the Instron universal test machine. Load and strain readings are taken at discrete intervals until fracture occurs. The small area of the specimen that is fixed in the clamp area and does not carry the load into the specimen but acts only to force the specimen into axial alignment. The compressive load is applied through the end of the specimen an area 0.4" x 0.1".

FIGURE 6. SCHEMATIC OF CONCENTRIC CYLINDER COMPRESSION FIXTURE

Experiments have shown that the geometrical perfection of the specimen end is very important. Specimens containing a chamfer to remove the machining burrs have a significantly reduced area to carry the load and the compressive ultimate is only ~70% of the ultimate strength found for perfectly prepared specimens.

A second type of compression test was conducted using a modification of the ITTRI fixture. The specimen size is 4" length with 1-3/4" of each end being tabbed to provide an unsupported gage length of 1/2". Two specimen widths (.25" and .50") were used. The load is introduced by the wedge effect of the collets through shear at the tabs into the side surfaces of the specimen end.

The third method of obtaining the compressive stress strain response utilizes the honeycomb core sandwich beam loaded in 4 point bending. The test set-up follows ASTM C-393 in general. A one-half size beam specimen was designed by Materials Sciences Corporation (17) to enable a specimen to be cut from the largest size composite panels. The test specimen is shown schematically in Figure 7. It consists of a .040" thick compression skin 1/2" wide x 11" long bonded on the top of aluminum honeycomb. The tension skin is .080" thick titanium 6Al-4V for tests of Gr/Al in the longitudinal direction; transverse tests use .02" thick titanium. The specimen containing 0° and 90° strain gages is loaded in 4 point bend with a load span of 4" and a reaction span of 10". Since the moment is constant for the area between the loading noses, a relatively large area of the specimen is tested which tends to minimize local defects.

The specimens are prepared by adhesively bonding the skins to the core at elevated temperature in a fixture which provides the precise alignment of tension and compression skins.

Figure 7. SANDWICH BEAM COMPRESSION TEST SPECIMEN.

The beam is loaded in discrete increments and the strains readout at each load level to provide a stress strain curve. The restraint of Poisson strains contributed by the adhesive bond to the core and the contribution of the core shear stiffness are an unknown quantity and are not factored into the calculation of stress and skin strains.

The stress in the skin is computed using the following relationship:

$$\sigma_c = \frac{P}{2} \times \frac{M}{b \times t_c \times T}$$

where: ;

- σ_c = Compressive stress—PSI
- P = Load applied to the load noses—pounds
- M = Moment Length (support span—load span) \div 2, in.
- b = Width of compression skin—in 2
- t_c = Thickness of Compression skin—in
- t_t = Thickness of tension skin—in
- T = Effective beam thickness

$$T = \text{Beam Thickness} - \frac{t_c}{2} - \frac{t_t}{2}$$

In general, the sandwich beam specimen results for both strength and modulus are slightly higher than the values obtained by other test methods. As an approximation, the values are ~12% higher.

Shear Strength and Modulus

The 15° off axis tensile test specimen was recommended to NETCO by Material Sciences Corporation for the determination of shear stress-strain response. The test specimen is made up like a tensile specimen except that the fiber direction is oriented 15° to the edges of the specimen. The specimen width is increased to 0.5" and the gage length is increased to 7.0". A detailed discussion of the design of the test specimen for Gr/Al is given in reference (17).

Table II. Summary of Room Temperature
Mechanical Properties for Three Gr/Al Systems

	<u>T50/201 Baseline</u>	<u>HM3000-3/201</u>	<u>Gy70/201</u>
Type of Laminate	3 Layers	4 Layers	3 Layer
Fiber Volume Fraction	0.30	0.34	0.31
Mechanical Properties	**	**	**
E_{11}^T , MSI	19.7(22)	19.1(22.5)	30.6(34.3)
F_{11}^T , KSI	82.4	117	92.4
E_{11}^C , MSI	19.1*		
F_{11}^C , KSI	76.8*		
E_{22}^T , MSI	4.8		
F_{22}^T , KSI	4.5	4.2	6.3
E_{22}^C , MSI	6.4*		
F_{22}^C , KSI	48.5*		
τ_{12} , KSI	6.3		
G_{12} , MSI	3.1		
γ_{12} ,	0.31		
γ_{21} ,	0.055		

Key:

* = Monolayer Configuration
 E = Elastic Modulus
 T = Tensile
 C = Compression
 11= Longitudinal
 22= Transverse
 τ = Shear

** = values in () are for liquid nitrogen stabilized
 F = Ultimate Strength
 G = Shear Modulus
 γ_{21} =Minor Poisson Ratio
 γ_{12} =Major Poisson Ratio

Results and Discussion

The mechanical behavior of the baseline (3 layers) configuration of the T-50/201 system has been extensively characterized at room temperature. Hundreds of tests have been conducted in order to begin to build a meaningful data base on tensile, shear, and compressive properties. An extensive review of this data is presented in reference (17). For the purpose of this paper we will merely summarize the room temperature properties in order to provide a reference for an understanding of the effects of temperature on these properties. The room temperature properties for three different graphite fiber SYSTEMS (T50, GY70, HM 3000-3) are given in TABLE II. The data for the celanese (GY70) and the Hercules (HM 3000-3) composite systems are quite limited but they do demonstrate the excellent translation of fiber properties into the composite structure.

Data obtained from load cycling experiments indicate that the magnitude of the elastic tensile modulus is dependent upon load history, i.e. an increase of ~20% is observed for specimens previously loaded to 50% of their ultimate tensile strength. This change in modulus is essentially complete after one cycle of loading; second and subsequent load applications to the same stress level produce no additional changes in the stress/strain curve. The magnitude of the modulus increase varies but is not linearly proportional to the percent of ultimate strength reached in the first load cycle. Specimens loaded to stress levels corresponding to 22, 44, and 78% of ultimate tensile strength exhibited tensile moduli increases of 4%, 14%, and 35% respectively. Immersion of test specimens in liquid nitrogen prior to testing affects specimens similarly. Data from preliminary heat treating studies have shown equivalent (~20%) increases in tensile moduli when conventional T-6 heat treatments are employed for the matrix alloy.

The effects of temperature on the longitudinal tensile strength and modulus of T50/201 baseline composites is shown in Figure 8. Similar data for the HM 3000-3/201 and GY70/201 SYSTEMS are shown in Figures 9 and 10 respectively. Tensile data from all these SYSTEMS are plotted in Figure 8. The longitudinal ultimate tensile strength is relatively unaffected (i.e. less than a 10% reduction) at temperatures up to 600°F. Experimentally it has been observed that random failures do occur outside the hot zone whenever test temperatures are 600°F or lower. At higher temperatures the decrease in strength becomes more pronounced. In the T-50/201 SYSTEM, at 700°F the decrease is 16% and at 900°F the reduction in room temperature tensile strength is 30%. In the HM 3000-3/201 SYSTEM the reduction of UTS at 700°F is somewhat greater, 22% whereas the GY70/201 SYSTEM exhibits a 700°F reduction in UTS of only 11%.

The transverse properties of the various Gr/Al families are dominated by the low strength of the fiber/matrix interface and this interfacial failure mode predominates to temperatures in excess of 500°F.

At significantly higher temperatures (700°-900°F) the transverse behavior of the composite approximates that of the aluminum alloy matrix, i.e. the failure mode shifts from one of interface control to a matrix dominated failure. The elevated temperature transverse tensile strength of T50/201 baseline composites is shown below:

TEMPERATURE, °F	70	500	600	700	800	900
Transverse Tensile, KSI	4.5	4.0	3.5	3.0	2.5	1.0

The stress/strain behavior of the various Gr/Al families shows little or no real decrease up to 500°F. The stress/strain response is not quite linearly elastic to fracture for the longitudinal orientation. However, the composite clearly reflects the predominance of the fibers which are elastic to fracture.

Figure 8. STRENGTH AND MODULUS OF T50/201 AL. AS A FUNCTION OF TEMPERATURE.

Figure 9. STRENGTH AND MODULUS OF HM 3000-3/201 AL. AS A FUNCTION OF TEMPERATURE

Figure 10. STRENGTH AND MODULUS OF GY 70/201 AL. AS A FUNCTION OF TEMPERATURE

Figure 11. GR/AL STRENGTH VS. TEMPERATURE—ALL SYSTEMS

Discontinuous SiC/Al Composites

The predicted room temperature tensile moduli and Poisson's ratio for various concentrations of silicon carbide whiskers in 2024 aluminum alloys is shown in Figure 12 (reference 20). For composites containing a nominal 25% whisker loading the predicted value of the tensile modulus is 16 MSI; the experimentally measured values range from 15.2 to 17.2 msi. Predicted moduli for composite billets containing 30% and 40% whisker loadings are 17.5 msi and 20.8 msi respectively. The corresponding experimentally observed moduli range from 14.4 to 19.4 msi.

The agreement between the predicted and measured values for composites containing < 30% SiC is good. For whisker concentrations > 30 v/o SiC the experimental values are 10 to 20% lower than predicted. Porosity is suspected in these higher volume loadings.

A limited number of elevated temperature tensile tests were conducted at 500°F. Most composite specimens exhibited tensile strengths in the range of 28 to 32 ksi. These results are rather disappointing since they indicate that the 500°F properties are only 40 to 60% of the room temperature properties.

Figure 12. Predicted Tensile Modulus and Poisson's Ratio for Short Fiber Material (SiC/Al) After Rosen, Ref. (20).

Summary

Data have been presented which indicate that significant property enhancement is possible using graphite fiber reinforced aluminum alloys. Good translation of fiber properties has been achieved. It has been shown that a family of Gr/Al materials is available which offers a wide range of improved properties over aluminum alloys both at room and elevated temperatures.

Acknowledgment

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